

1 **ETS factor induction during differentiation in the human embryo.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification of
9 ETS family transcription factors lineage commitment factors in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Yamamoto, H., Flannery, M.L., Kupriyanov, S., Pearce, J., McKercher, S.R., Henkel, G.W., Maki,
12 R.A., Werb, Z. and Oshima, R.G., 1998. Defective trophoblast function in mice with a targeted mutation of
13 Ets2. *Genes & development*, 12(9), pp.1315-1326.

14 2. Wen, F., Tynan, J.A., Cecena, G., Williams, R., Múnera, J., Mavrothalassitis, G. and Oshima,
15 R.G., 2007. Ets2 is required for trophoblast stem cell self-renewal. *Developmental biology*, 312(1),
16 pp.284-299.